

Social Studies and Economics Teacher Qualification, Knowledge on Usage of Collaborative –Instructional-Strategy Skill in Selected Secondary Schools, Zone-B, Benue State: Evaluation and Counselling Inference

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Abstract

The study investigates social studies and economics teachers' qualification, knowledge on usage of collaboration instructional strategy skill in some selected secondary school in zone B area of Benue state: the evaluation and counselling Inference. Four research questions and four null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. A survey research design was employed for the study. A total of thirty six social studies and economics teachers as respondent were selected from twenty secondary schools in zone B of Benue State using a simple random sampling technique to constitute the sample size. Instrument for data collection was Social Studies, Economics Teacher Disposition to Collaborative Instructional Strategy (SSETDCIS). Data collected were analyzed using chi-square. The result revealed that social studies and economics teachers' qualification and knowledge do significantly affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy among others. Based on the findings, it was suggested and counselled that teachers' qualification and knowledge should go beyond celebration of certificate other than what they can do or teach, to use the prerequisite knowledge mastery competence to adopt this strategy in social studies and economics class and that the unqualified social studies and economics teachers who do not adopt this strategy in class should often go for training, workshop and seminar to be acquainted with the usage of collaborative instructional strategy. If this is done, it will encourage the teachers to adopt the strategy in other to make the learners visible, attentive, vibrant in class, active participants in learning process, encourage group work, sharing ideas while the teacher supervises and provides idea for discourse.

Keywords: Social Studies, Economics, Teacher Qualification, Knowledge, Collaborative Instructional Strategy, Evaluation, Counselling.

Introduction

A teacher is someone who transmits knowledge to one who desires that knowledge. This transmission can be formally or informally done using divers techniques which includes counseling and evaluation. Teachers form a central point of any educational endeavors. They implement educational policies and curriculum. They play a vital role in the attainment of the goals of every educational system at all levels of education including evaluating educational program and providing counseling to students. This is confirmed by the

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Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN, 2013) statement in her education policy that no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers, and backed up by Garba, Teryima and Wilfred-Bonse (2021) argument that teachers are crucial to the survival of every school system. This includes evaluating students' academic work and providing counseling to students. These statements are indications that teachers are indispensable components of educational system.

The societal expectation is that before one becomes a teacher the person must have acquired superior knowledge that will qualify him/her to be a teacher. The process of passing or transmitting this superior knowledge to the learners is called teaching. According to Agogo (2020), teaching involves the mastery of an extensive repertoire of skills without which, no matter how penetrating a person's intellectual capacities may be the person will be pedagogically inept. By implication, the aim of teaching is not just to pass and transmit information but to also transform students from passive recipients of others knowledge into active constructors of their own and other's knowledge. This can be achieved through evaluation and counselling of students. This includes engaging the students in learning which includes evaluating them as well as counselling them on carrier choice or getting students involve in the active construction of knowledge. This means that a teacher may not succeed adequately in transforming the students without the students' active participation.

According to Elvis (2014) the essence of teaching is to improve students' academic performance, instill in the student intrinsic motivation to learn, behavior modification, instill positive action into students' cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning domains, develop all-rounded students (physically, intellectually, psychologically, socially and emotionally) and to promote good mental health in students among others. This can only be achieved by competent qualified teacher who not only know what to teach but how to teach it well (Muodumogu,2004) in social studies and economics class, using an adequate teaching strategy which includes evaluative and counselling to drive home the points in class.

It should be noted that some teachers have the certificate but have not acquired prerequisite knowledge mastery competence in a particular field. Sar (2019) argued that such people are not qualified teachers in that field. However, the capabilities of teachers with the same qualification differ from one school to another. Some teachers though qualified in their field celebrate their certificate instead of what they can teach. Characteristic of teachers' quality include verbal ability, counselling, subject matter competence, knowledge of teaching methods (Pedagogy), adopting adequate evaluation strategy that covers the three domain of learning and ability to use a wide range of teaching strategies to enhance or stimulate learning (Agogo 2020). Therefore, the extent of achieving the aims and objectives of teaching maximally may be largely dependent on the kind of teaching strategy often employed by teachers, especially social studies and economics teachers in secondary schools and the level of engagement of students in the teaching-learning process. In social studies teaching for instance , inquiry method as one of the teaching strategy is encouraged mostly to guide student to ask questions and discover things in their environment (Zaria & Bulya,2011). It is the teaching strategy that encourages active participatory by students.

The teaching strategy as noted by Opara and Ihekoronye (2020) could be teacher-centered or learner-centered. Teacher-centered strategy is the type that consist of teacher being the main authority figure in the class while the students are perceived as being empty vessels whose main role is to passively received information for the purpose of assessment. In learner-centered strategies on the other hand both teachers and students play an equally active role in the learning process.

Okafor (2014) stated that, the application of learner-centered teaching strategies ensure that learning is collaborative, interactive, active, participative, practical and engaging; thereby promoting students' retention, remembrance, academic performance as well as reducing boredom and abstract learning. In other words the teaching/learning atmosphere should not be for too much talking by the teacher but too much of action, with an increase in budgetary allocation to the subsector, with an increase in information dissemination programmes as stressed in the national policy on education (FRN,2004), that all

teachers should be professionally trained and intellectually well equipped. This includes teaching social studies and economics class in secondary schools. Since social studies and economics teaching/learning encourages team work and inquiry method of teaching for adaptability in the environment of the learners, the need for the knowledge, usage and application of collaborative instructional strategy in class should be utmost in social studies and economics lesson delivery. This could be achieved by an effective competent and qualified teacher who according to Muodumogu (2004) does not only know what to teach but how to teach it well. Thus, collaborative instruction strategy is a teaching strategy that emphasizes joint intellectual efforts by students. It entails bringing together learners of diverse abilities, both fast and slow learners or levels of comprehension to study together for the purpose of interacting and generating their knowledge by themselves with the teacher playing a supervisory role. Johnson and Holybec (2018), argued that a collaborative instruction does not just involves bringing the students to sit in groups but is rather encourages working and interacting together to achieve collaborative work goals. It is the teacher's duty to create a conducive classroom which typifies cooperation and good understanding among the students. Laal and Ghodsi (2012), maintained that in order to ensure that collaborative instruction is successfully carried out, the teachers should emphasize on basic element such as positive interdependence, understanding, individual responsibilities, direct interaction, friendliness and active participation by every group member. In other word every student participation should be the watch word by the teachers.

Dooly (2018) noted that collaborative instructional strategy is a medium through which the whole teaching – learning process is highly interactive and cooperative, as students teach the teacher, students teach one another and the teacher teaches the student in return, mostly in areas the student finds difficult. It is a shift from the teacher centered which entails teacher dominating the whole lesson process to other processes that involves student discussion, full participation and active work with the course material (Wilfred-Bonse, Ogwuche & Okochi, 2019; Wilfred-Bonse, Aboho & Ogwuche, 2019). This is supported by the popular Chinese proverb which states that:

What I hear, I forget
What I see, I remember
What I do, I understand

What this entails is that until a child practices a concept or participates in the learning process, he cannot fully understand the concept.

Collaborative instructional strategy is firmly rooted in constructivist theory which stresses that knowledge can be created within a population where members actively interact by sharing experiences and take on asymmetry roles. It is a teaching strategy that stresses on joints intellectual effort by students while the teacher supervises. Here the teachers split the class into two or more working groups depending on the class size for the students to engage in mutual search for knowledge and understanding or finding solutions to identified problem in the class (Mitnik, Recabarren, Nussbaum & Soto, 2019).

Collaborative instructional strategy therefore involves:

Learners to always think outside the box by putting on their thinking caps.

Learners - centered activities should be encouraged.

Learners full participation and involvement in class activities, especially when materials are available in good states, and shapes, should be sustained.

Students are visible and vibrant in class.

Students are attentive and active participants in the learning process.

Students are participatory in lesson/activities.

Learning positively affects learners' values, self-worth, commitment and identities (Adedoyin 2011)

Encourage creativity and original thinking.

Encourage career-orienting knowledge by them put on their thinking cap, to think creatively.

Flexibility in teaching.

Encouragement of group works/sharing ideas.

Take initiatives where learners are thinkers and potentials.

Teaching is based on students' full involvement in the learning process.

The teachers should be a facilitator, mentor and idea provider for discourse.

The teacher teaches the learner how to think and own their learning

He should build the environment as a potential for thinking and recreation.

Moreover, the gap between teachers' qualification, knowledge and their usage of interactive learners centered instructions strategy for lesson delivery in class, especially in social studies and economics, that will make the learners, active participatory in lesson process to discover things themselves, seem to have become a worrisome situation and a great concern to many observers and stake holders in education. It is noted that some teachers have the certificate but have not acquired prerequisite knowledge mastery competence in social studies and economics in using collaborative instructional strategy (Opera & Ihekoronye,2021) for social studies and economics teaching. It is further noted that some social studies and economics teachers celebrate their certificate instead of what they can do or teach to achieve team teaching or use inquiry method of teaching which is an aspect of collaborative instructional strategy that should be employable in lesson delivery in social studies and economics class. Some authorities like Opera & Ihekoronye (2021), Moudumogu (2004) and Agogo (2021) have approached teachers' qualification and usage of collaborative instructional strategy skill from conceptual viewpoints with little reporting on empirical research. Hence the researcher deemed it necessary to approach the topic empirically and to research on how teachers' qualification and knowledge can affect the usage of collaborative instructional strategy. Only a well research work can actually determine the extent to which such factors may affect the usage of collaborative teaching strategy skills in class. Based on this, this study sought to investigate social studies and economics teachers' qualification, knowledge and their usage of collaborative instructional strategy skills for lesson delivery in social studies class and the counselling and evaluative inference.

Research Questions

In line with each specific objective, the following research questions guided the study.

- i. To what extent do social studies and economics teacher qualification affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy?
- ii. To what extent do social studies economics teachers' knowledge affect the usage of collaborative instructional strategy?

Research Hypothesis

Based on the research questions raised the null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: Social Studies and economics teachers' qualification has no significant effect on their usage of collaborative Instructional strategy.

HO₂: Social Studies and economics teachers' knowledge has no significant effect on their usage of collaborative instructional strategy skill.

Materials and Methods

Descriptive survey research design was employed for study. The population for the study comprised of all social studies and economics Secondary school teachers of zone B in Benue state formed the population for the study. Hence, the population consisted of 43 teachers in twenty secondary schools in Zone B of Benue State. The sample for the study were selected using the simple random sampling technique. In the process a sample of 22 teachers were selected which comprises of ten (10) Bachelor Degree Holders and twelve (12) Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) Holders. A 12-item questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Social Studies and Economics Teacher's Qualification and Knowledge on the Collaborative Instructional Strategy (QOSETEQAKOC) was developed by the researchers. The questionnaire consisted of three sections: A and B. Section A elicited information on teacher's bio data information such as such as academic qualification and teacher experience. While Section B comprises of 5 items which elicited information on the extent to which teacher qualification affect the use of collaborative instructional strategy section C is made up of 5 items for ascertaining the extent to which teacher knowledge affect the use of collaborative instructional strategy. the instrument was validated by three experts in social studies and economics and research who examined the instrument with regards to appropriateness (face validity) and comprehensiveness (content validity). In the process a validity index of 0.78 was obtained. The instrument was further subjected to pilot and the process yielded a reliability co-efficient of 0.75 from the statistical result of the instrument tested was used for the study, indicating that the instrument used for the study was reliable. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation and t-test statistics.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: to what extent do social studies and economics teacher qualification affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation showing extent to which Social Studies and Economics Teachers Qualification Affect their usage of Collaborative Instructional Strategy.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	STD DEV	Remarks
1	Teacher qualification exerts a high level of effect on their use of collaborative instructional strategy.	10	5	4	3	3.00	0.78	Agree
2	Teachers with low qualification are not proficient in the use of collaborative instructional strategy	12	4	3	3	3.14	0.82	Disagree
3	Teachers' qualification does not necessarily affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy	8	8	4	2	3.37	0.96	Agree

4	Teacher qualification affects their awareness and competence in the use of collaborative instructional strategy	10	5	4	3	3.00	0.78	Agree
5	Using unqualified teachers to teach social studies and economics may undermine their effective use of collaborative instructional strategy	10	5	4	3	3.00	0.78	Agree
Mean						3.10	0.82	

Table 1 above shows the extent to which social studies and economics teacher qualification affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy. Results indicate that an average mean of 3.10 was obtained based on the response to the items. This value is above the benchmark value 2.50 for a four-point likert scale questionnaire. Hence, social studies and economics teacher qualification affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy to high extent.

Research Question 1: to what extent do social studies and economics teachers' knowledge affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation showing extent to which Social Studies and Economics Teachers Knowledge Affect their usage of Collaborative Instructional Strategy.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	STD DEV	Remarks
6	Teacher knowledge exerts a high level of effect on their use of collaborative instructional strategy.	8	8	4	2	3.37	0.96	Agree
7	Poor teacher knowledge hinders effective use of collaborative instructional strategy	4	8	4	6	2.45	1.04	Disagree
8	Teachers' knowledge does not necessarily affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy	8	8	4	2	3.03	0.96	Agree
9	Teacher knowledge affects their awareness and competence in the use of collaborative instructional strategy	12	4	3	3	3.14	0.82	Agree

10	Teachers with adequate knowledge of social studies and economics achieve more in terms of learning outcomes when they employ the use of collaborative instructional strategy	10	5	4	3	3.00	0.78	Agree
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Mean	2.65	1.02
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Table 2 above shows the extent to which social studies and economics teacher qualification affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy. Results indicate that an average mean of 3.00 was obtained based on the response to the items. This value is above the benchmark value 2.50 for a four-point Likert scale questionnaire. Hence, social studies and economics teacher qualification affect their usage of collaborative instructional strategy to high extent.

Hypotheses 1

Social studies and economics teachers' qualification has no significant effect on the use of collaborative instructional strategy.

Table 1: t-test statistics on the effect of Teachers qualification on the usage of collaborative instructional strategy

Variables	N	Mean	t-cal	sig	Decision	Conclusion
Teacher Qualification	22	3.10	12.32	0.021	Reject H ₀	Significant
Collaborative Instructional Strategy	22	3.10				

Table 1 indicates the t-test statistics for determining the effect of teachers' qualification on teacher qualification collaborative instructional strategy. Results show that means that that calculated value was given as 12.32. The p-value at 0.021 was found to be less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis 1 is rejected indicating social studies and economics teachers' qualification has a significant effect on the use of collaborative instructional strategy.

Hypotheses 1

Social studies and economics teachers' knowledge have no significant effect on the use of collaborative instructional strategy.

Table 2: t-test statistics on the effect of Teachers Knowledge on the usage of collaborative instructional strategy

Variables	N	Mean	t-cal	sig	Decision	Conclusion
Teacher Knowledge	22	2.65	17.33	0.022	Reject H ₀	Significant
Collaborative Instructional Strategy	22	2.65				

Table 2 indicates the t-test statistics for determining the effect of teachers' knowledge on teacher qualification collaborative instructional strategy. Results show that means that that calculated value was given as 17.33. The p-value at 0.022 was found to be less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis 1 is rejected indicating social studies and economics teachers' qualification has a significant effect on the use of collaborative instructional strategy.

Conclusion

The result of this study has shown that social studies and economics teachers' qualifications and knowledge have significance effect on the usage of collaborative instructional strategy in class. This is because social studies and economics teachers who are qualified and knowledgeable in the discipline have acquired the expertise of using inquiry method which is an aspect of collaborative instructional strategy in teaching more than the unqualified social studies and economics teachers, however some qualified and knowledgeable social studies and economics teachers who have the expertise and know-how in teaching social studies seem to celebrate their certificate other than what they can do or teach (Sar,2019). Social Studies and economics teachers who are not specialist in the discipline do not use collaborative instructional strategy. Most use lecture method (Zaria & Bulya,2011) while those in the discipline who are acquainted with the skill most times do not use it. They see it as a waste of time. Social studies and economics teachers often attend workshop and seminar on the usage of collaborative instructional strategy when access government fund but on other occasion they do not. These set of teachers have the certificate but have not acquired the prerequisite knowledge mastery competence (Agogo, 2020) and so lack the expertise for using collaborative instructional strategy in class.

Therefore, since qualification and knowledge affect the usage of collaborative instructional strategy in class, qualified and knowledgeable social studies and economics teachers who have undergone social studies and economics training should be cancelled and made to teach social studies and economics, in other to demonstrate the strategy in class since social studies and economics training involves the usage of inquiry method which is the part of collaborative instructional strategy. Qualified and knowledgeable Social Studies and economics teachers should use their knowledge to adopt the strategy in class instead of celebrating their certificate.

Also, all social studies and economics teachers should use collaborative instructional strategy to enable students' participation in class and to discover things themselves about the environment since social studies for instance is the study of man in the environment. Government should provide fund for Social Studies and economics teachers to often attend seminar and workshop on the usage of collaborative instructional strategy for success in class. If this is done it will encourage the teachers to adopt the strategy in other to make the learners visible, attentive, vibrant in class, active participants in learning process, encourage group work, sharing ideas while the teacher supervises and provides ideas for discourse.

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